

1. LDGAT1 1 MEGSGKGDSPSSALSVAVPADAAPAKLSALEAENARLRDVLRSRQKPEYTSYGYLYKYPPEPSAETKYQWDRWII
2. AIDGAT1
3. BnDGAT1
4. HsDGAT1
5. MmDGAT1

80 90 100 110 120 130 140

1. LDGAT1 **YVNSLVAFQYKPKDAVYHPRGHVNVGCTLVVVEGDKRKAAYWRFQVWFDPRGTGASLLRLSLQDQKRAEEMVQHF**
2. AIDGAT1 **MAIIFDSAG----VTTVTVENGSGGFVLDLDRF**
3. BnDGAT1 **MAVIFDSGG----MAVPEENG----VADLDRF**
4. HsDGAT1
5. MmDGAT1

150 160 170 180 190 200 210

1. LDGAT1 **VDAGCHKRILNASYRNRSSPPRSADIRWNOGATSSEDPACSTGRHPPSPVPGSVNRFLLDAORWVVASAGASAGSAGS**
2. AIDGAT1 **RRR-----KSSGDS--SINGLLSGGDINSDPDDVGE---APA--DVRDRISVWINDAQEACQSTANLFGSD**
3. BnDGAT1 **HRR-----KSSGDS--SINGLLS--DDEPSDDVGE---AAAADARDRVSDAWSEECACQSTANLFGSD**
4. HsDGAT1 **MGDI-----SSRRRRTGSRPSSRHGGGGP-----AAAEVEVDRDAAGDPVAGAGC**
5. MmDGAT1 **MGDRGGAGSSRRRRTGSRVSVVQGGSP-----KVEEDEVRDAVSDPLGAGC**

220 230 240 250 260 270 280 290 300

1. LDGAT1 **SVSTGTGYSSESGLSEAGTQPQPARQASNLRFPAQPADKAKRGPILCSLTMHTVRSRSLDHRHMMATQHSGLF**
2. AIDGAT1 **-----NGGGDNNNGGRGCEGRGNADAAFTTYRE-----SVPARRHFARESPLSSDAIQKHSHGLE**
3. BnDGAT1 **---TETRES---GGRGG---GNGDVFRTYRE-----SVPARRHFARESPLSSDAIQKHSHGLE**
4. HsDGAT1 **APAPAPN---KDDAGVCGSHWBLRCHR-----LQDSLSSSSGSSN-YRFL**
5. MmDGAT1 **APAPAPAPAHTRDKDERTSVGDGYWDLRCHR-----LQDSLSSSSGSSN-YRFL**

300 310 320 330 340 350 360

1. LDGAT1 **NLDMVAVFAANRQAVIENLLKYGLIANDAGWVSAVVTKGNVWDLTKWLDLAFVFTYAIYALVLVGCARLEAER**
2. AIDGAT1 **NLGMVAVIAVANSRQVIFENLLKYGLIIRTDFWFSSTLSR---DDELFLMCCISLSSPLFAATVTRLL**
3. BnDGAT1 **NLGMVAVIAVANSRQVIFENLLKYGLIIRTDFWFSSTLSR---DDELFLMCCISLSSPLFAATVTRLL**
4. HsDGAT1 **NLGMVAVIILSARQVIFENLLKYGLIIVDPIQVMSLLFLKDPYSVPEAPCLVLAANVAVAAVQVRR**
5. MmDGAT1 **NLGMVAVITLISARQVIFENLLKYGLIIVDPIQVMSLLFLKDPYSVPEAPCVTIASNIVAVVQVRR**

370 380 390 400 410 420 430

1. LDGAT1 **KAGIAKRKKEISPSDAKRRAAAMGRLETERLWMLINFNANSAALLPFCVMVFATNADPAPCGVVMMLT-VLLWM**
2. AIDGAT1 **-----LQKYSRPPVIVRHIIITMPPVIVYVYVTRCCDSAFLESVGTMMHDT-CHVWF**
3. BnDGAT1 **-----VLQRTSPVPAIIVHVIITLPEVLYVYVTRCCDSAFLESVGTMMHDT-CHVWF**
4. HsDGAT1 **LAVGALTQAGLILRHVAVLAILCFLAAVVVLVESITVPGVSLAAHMAHTLTF**
5. MmDGAT1 **LAVGALTQMGLLRHVVNLAAILCFLAAVAHVLESITVPGVVFVAASYSMTF**

440 450 460 470 480 490 500 510

1. LDGAT1 **KRFVSAHCNQDYSMARREGVLRPGERGSDAPIREGGPALAMENITLTMKAVVVAQVGVYQAPAYFSRKR**
2. AIDGAT1 **KRFVSAHTSYDRLSLAN-----AADANR-----EVMV---YVSLKSAFAGVVAQVGVYQAPAYFSRKR**
3. BnDGAT1 **KRFVSAHTSYDRLSLAN-----SADANR-----ETSM---YVSLKSAFAGVVAQVGVYQAPAYFSRKR**
4. HsDGAT1 **KRFVSAHVSNSWRRLRARAKAAS---AGKASASAAAPHYSSMDDLTYRSLKAFGLFAQVGVYQAPAYFSRKR**
5. MmDGAT1 **KRFVSRDYNLWRRLRRVKAQAVS---TGRVSGAAAQQAVMSDDLTYRSLKAFGLFAQVGVYQAPAYFSRKR**

520 530 540 550 560 570 580

1. LDGAT1 **MRWIMRVRVLELLELTIGIMFVSVBQYATETISNLSLABIQDLDNPRYLVSEVIRKALLETLYCQGLIGSDFEHLWVW**
2. AIDGAT1 **RGVVABQFAKLVYETIGFMGEGEIRKNTNIVRSHHLGSLGLLYABSEVIRKALLETLYCQGLIGSDFEHLWVW**
3. BnDGAT1 **RGVVABQFAKLVYETIGFMGEGEIRKNTNIVRSHHLGSLGLLYABSEVIRKALLETLYCQGLIGSDFEHLWVW**
4. HsDGAT1 **RRFLRIRLEMLPQQVGLLQGMVVTIQRNKRRPDDNYSRIEELIKGAAVNHLLTQATFQWYLAHSAVW**
5. MmDGAT1 **RRFLRIRVLEMLPQQVGLLQGMVVTIQRNKRRPDDNYSRIEELIKGAAVNHLLTQATFQWYLAHSAVW**

590 600 610 620 630 640 650

1. LDGAT1 **LLGFARAGCGRDEPKKRNNSTTTDDVARTNMPVHKMMSHVQSPVVRAGAPRNTAMLLMVSVSAVHEHIVMG**
2. AIDGAT1 **LLAEFCRCGRDEPKKRNNAKASVGDYRMMNMPVHKMMVSHVQSPVVRAGAPRNTAMLLMVSVSAVHEHIVMG**
3. BnDGAT1 **LLAEFCRCGRDEPKKRNNAKASVGDYRMMNMPVHKMMVSHVQSPVVRAGAPRNTAMLLMVSVSAVHEHIVMG**
4. HsDGAT1 **AVAFRCRCGRDEPKKRNNSVSTYFQCNWNPVHKMMVSHVQSPVVRAGAPRNTAMLLMVSVSAVHEHIVMG**
5. MmDGAT1 **AVAFRCRCGRDEPKKRNNAESVSTYFQCNWNPVHKMMVSHVQSPVVRAGAPRNTAMLLMVSVSAVHEHIVMG**

660 670 680 690 700 710 720 730

1. LDGAT1 **LDLHVGMWSPVQWARFVSNPGLPSSWSIQWPIAFLFCIRFPQVPIEATRYLCARIQNAVCENIIFQVCHFCIG**
2. AIDGAT1 **VVPCSL--KRFW---AFLFCIRFPQVPIEATRYLCARIQNAVCENIIFQVCHFCIG**
3. BnDGAT1 **VVPCSL--KRFW---AFLFCIRFPQVPIEATRYLCARIQNAVCENIIFQVCHFCIG**
4. HsDGAT1 **VVPLRM--RWFW---AFLFCIRFPQVPIEATRYLCARIQNAVCENIIFQVCHFCIG**
5. MmDGAT1 **VVPLRM--RWFW---AFLFCIRFPQVPIEATRYLCARIQNAVCENIIFQVCHFCIG**

740 750 753

1. LDGAT1 **EVSIIMMYVHDCVWLNRR**
2. AIDGAT1 **EMCVVLLVYHDLMNRKGSMS**
3. BnDGAT1 **EMCVVLLVYHDLMNRKGSMS**
4. HsDGAT1 **EVAVIMMYVHDCVWLNRYEAPAEA**
5. MmDGAT1 **EVAVIMMYVHDCVWLNRYEAPAEA**